

Towards 3D Flexible 6G Networks: Status, Challenges and Technical Enablers

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Abstract— It is a key challenge and obligation for future networks to deliver high-quality wireless for enabling novel services and application to flourish for the benefit of humans on a personal level, for society as a whole, as well as for business and innovation. The dynamics, as well as the heterogeneity of the foreseen 6G system in terms of communication technologies, frequencies used, management frameworks, etc. make the need for flexibility of utmost importance. Although several steps are being made to this direction, flexible networks, capable of dynamically adapting to changes, (re)configuring themselves, exploiting highly dynamic resources in terms of availability in a three-dimensional network space is still a challenge from different perspectives. This paper identifies the key challenges, technical enablers, as well as current efforts towards the realization of the 3D, flexible 6G “network of networks” concept.

Keywords—3D networks, flexible infrastructure as a service, programmability, controllability

I. INTRODUCTION

6G is defined with the high-level goal of having an intrinsic support to the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals (UN-SDGs) [1]. Specifically, for diverse goals including good health and well-being, quality education, economic growth, innovation, reduced inequalities, sustainable cities and communities, life on land, etc., future networks must have the role of a key driver. Moreover, the Key Value Indicators (KVIs), which have been driving the first steps of the wireless and mobile systems’ evolution [2], such as digital inclusiveness and sustainability, already clearly point to the way forward towards the next system design considerations.

6G systems are expected to support an unprecedented variety of novel services, requiring extreme performance and pervading through every aspect of human lives and society. Complex business value chains, stakeholders’ diverse goals and business perspectives, complicated interactions and relationships among members of the Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) ecosystem [3] are all synthesized within a highly fragmented technology landscape comprising numerous heterogeneous wired/wireless radio access network (RAN), edge, transport, core technologies, protocols, equipment vendors, Internet of Things (IoT) applications and protocols, data models, specifications, architectures, interfaces. Towards global scale connectivity and ultra-high capacity, capable to support the ultra-challenging futuristic use cases that 6G community already foresees [4], a disruptive paradigm

needs to be introduced, which will enable utmost flexibility, openness, programmability and controllability [5].

Ultra-flexible networks are expected to be one of the driving principles towards making the most of the available (diverse) resources, when and where available, across a three-dimensional (3D) connectivity-, computing- and intelligence-driven continuum. This continuum will ultimately lead to a network of networks [5], *unifying* -rather than solely *integrating* - flexibly deployable, moving or static diverse nodes synthesizing terrestrial, space, airborne, maritime, as well as underwater or underground networks, into one global, ubiquitous 3D RAN. Besides its geographical dimensioning, a true unification will create the required open interfaces for enabling diverse network architectures and communication structures, comprising mesh networks, device-to-device, and self-backhauling capabilities, as well as Non-Public Networks (NPNs) such as Campus/private networks [7] to seamlessly interoperate. Backward compatibility will be also crucial to enable a sustainable evolution -primarily from the cost perspective- unifying legacy/state-of-the-art technology (5G/beyond 5G, 4G, etc.) assets into the 3D network of networks’ unified resource pool, comprising connectivity, compute, memory, and storage resources, both physical (e.g., infrastructure-related), as well as virtual.

Flexible network topologies will support global coverage and limitless connectivity via (a) advanced networking technologies, such as mesh, nano technology networks, Non-Terrestrial Networks (NTNs), Device-to-Device (D2D), etc., (b) (sub)THz by using ultra-high frequencies in base stations, (c) new computing paradigms, exploiting dynamic multi-access edge computing (MEC) and more.

The first disruptive step towards enabling high network flexibility and programmability was already made with the adoption of the 5G Core (5GC) Service-Based Architecture (SBA) paradigm. The SBA of the 5GC network enables the 5GC control plane Network Functions (NFs) to expose Service-based Interfaces (SBIs) and act as service consumers or producers. This leads to a flexible deployment, where every NF allows other authorized NFs to access the services, thus enabling the consumption and exposure of services and capabilities to internal or external 3rd parties [8]. Nevertheless, so far, the scope of the SBA is only in the Core, omitting the RAN and transport segments, as well as the management system. Specifically for the latter, the Service Based Management Architecture (SBMA) is applied in a different manner than in the Core Network

(CN), in the sense that CN builds service discovery around Network Repository Function (NRF) whereas SBMA doesn't have such a service explicitly but multiple options instead. Further, SBMA doesn't define NFs but APIs only counter to CN control plane. Most importantly, RAN functionality is still defined by using classical means based on the concept of network entity and peer-to-peer interfaces rather than network functions and service interfaces as in the core network.

Besides the SBA paradigm, the well-established technologies of Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) have already paved the way for a highly dynamic network ecosystem, in which network functions, are decoupled from specific hardware, dynamically split, up/down scaled in terms of resources and according to (near) real time requirements. Nevertheless, there is still a long way forward for achieving the required flexibility and programmability towards addressing the envisioned 6G services and use cases. Recent, on-going and forthcoming standardization efforts have already identified diverse aspects and relevant enablers towards the above-discussed flexibility and programmability spanning across the different layers of the network, from the physical layer up to the management and orchestration. A discussion on the most relevant work items and studies is presented in the following section.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents an overview on recent, on-going, and forthcoming (planned) work items from 3GPP standardization work plan, as well as an overview of related works discussing diverse enablers on network flexibility, programmability, and controllability. Section III elaborates on the most critical technical requirements. Section IV presents the main technical enablers, concepts, and technologies towards the envisioned paradigm, while Section V discusses next steps and concludes this work.

II. STANDARDIZATION AND RELATED WORK

A. 3GPP Releases 16, 17 and 18.

Flexible network topologies and dynamic network traffic management has already been tackled since 3GPP Rel. 16 [8], in which the Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB) capability was introduced, i.e., a new wireless backhaul solution for 5G New Radio (NR), which is discussed in higher detail in the following section. Furthermore, Rel.16 introduced the NR sidelink concept (primarily addressing but not limited to Vehicle-to-Everything communications), which evolves the D2D concept, support for Access Traffic Steering, Switching and Splitting (ATSSS), initial studies on NPN support, as well as the first steps for satellite access. Furthermore, study on NR-based support for flexible access to unlicensed spectrum was initiated, while an enhanced common API framework for 3GPP northbound Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) was also released (CAPIF), for enabling flexible and efficient service exposure towards diverse industry sectors and verticals. Last but not least, the Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF) is introduced, which is considered the first step towards network intelligence.

Rel.17 [10] realizes enhancements to NR sidelink/D2D (such as single-hop, sidelink-based, L2 and L3 based UE-to-

Network (U2N) relaying capabilities), IAB enhancements, IoT and NR support over NTN, enhancements for NPNs - such as external credential support for standalone NPNs-, ATSSS support in the 5G system architecture, as well as the introduction of Unmanned Aerial Systems (UAS)-driven traffic management.

3GPP Rel. 18's workplan [11] -although still not finalised-, has already identified some relevant key work items on enhanced support of NPNs, Phase 2 studies on satellite access, study on satellite backhaul for the 5G system, ATSSS support in the 5G system architecture (Phase 3), UAS/Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) & Urban Air Mobility (UAM) (Phase 2), further NR sidelink relay, NR mobility and NR and IoT NTN enhancements, mobility management aspects for IAB nodes, air-to-ground network aspects for NR, while some initial steps for integrating Artificial Intelligence/Machine Learning (AI/ML) enablers for New Generation Radio Access Network (NG-RAN) management is also planned; as it will be discussed in the following sections, the AI/ML technology -especially if integrated as a native component of the system-can radically contribute to the flexibility and dynamic management aspects of the system. The table that follows provides an overview of the key recent, on-going, or planned work items and studies by 3GPP (TABLE I).

TABLE I KEY STANDARDIZATION WORK ITEMS TOWARDS FLEXIBLE BEYOND 5G/6G NETWORKS

3GPP Release	Relevant Work Item towards Network Flexibility
16	Integrated Access and Backhaul (IAB): multi-hop backhauling for flexible range extension, topology adaptation for link failure response, scalability to large number of UEs, over-the-air (OTA) sync, etc.
	NR sidelink: physical layer structure, resource allocation mode 1 and 2, cross-RAT and in-device coexistence, etc.
	Access Traffic Steering, Switching and Splitting (ATSSS): UE-UPF measurement functions for traffic steering, etc.
	Non-public Networks (NPN): support in NG-RAN, NPN cell selection/reselection, cell access control, etc.
	Satellite Access: Stage 1 only – not completed in Rel.16, moved to next Rel.
	Unlicensed spectrum: Flexible carrier aggregation, dual connectivity in licensed and shared spectrum, etc.
	CAPIF: Enhancement of 3GPP northbound APIs, registration with CAPIF Core Function to enable the discovery of the APIs by 3 rd party application servers, etc.
	Network Data Analytics Function (NWDAF)
17	NR sidelink/D2D/V2V enhancements: QoS aware power efficiency, DRX configuration, U2N relaying, etc.
	Integrated Access and Backhaul enhancements for NR
	IoT and NR support over NTNs: NB-IoT/eMTC
	Enhancements for NPN support: Support of Public Warning Systems (PWS), etc.
	ATSSS support in the 5G system architecture – Phase 2
18	Study on supporting UAS Connectivity, Identification, and Tracking, Application layer support for UAS, etc.
	Enhanced support for NPNs
	Study on 5GC enhancement for satellite access – Phase 2
	Study on support of Satellite Backhauling in 5GS
	ATSSS support enhancements – Phase 3
	UAS/UAV & UAM – Phase 2: Study on enhanced architecture for UAS, NR support for UAV, etc.
	NR sidelink relay enhancements, NR sidelink evolution
	NR and IoT NTN enhancements for Radio layer 2 and layer 3 Radio Resource Control
	Mobility enhancements for IAB
Air-to-ground aspects for NR	
AI/ML for NG-RAN: study on traffic characteristics and performance requirements for AI/ML model transfer, etc.	

Industry has also shown a great interest on several of the previous features, such as IAB [12][13], as key towards denser and more robust deployments; thus, it is expected that the evolution of such enablers during the next releases is going to be intense.

B. Related work from the literature

Besides the standardization efforts, several works have already been presented during the last three years, which focus on different aspects towards flexible, 3D networks, from physical layer enablers -such as RIS-driven 3D channel modelling and UAV-/UE-based mesh networks- up to the network and management layers, such as access steering, coverage extension, enhanced SDN-driven dynamic queue management, etc. ([12]-[25]).

Huq et al. [12] propose such an approach for the THz 6G system. Bai et al. [15] introduce a 3D geometry-based stochastic model for massive multiple input multiple output (mMIMO) millimetre wave (mmWave) UAV channels. To better represent the space-time non-stationarity in UAV scenarios, a novel UAV-related space-time cluster evolution algorithm is developed. Al-Ahmed et al. [16] exploit UAV base stations, along with wireless backhauling capabilities of the nodes in order to detect and address coverage holes in a given area. Q-learning is used for optimising the flexible UAV deployments at various angular positions to maximise the number of associated users per UAV-base station in the 3D network. Abdel-Basset et al. [17] introduce an algorithm for optimizing the coverage of UAV base stations, taking also advantage of available Reconfigurable Intelligent Surfaces (RIS) in the 3D space. Feng et al. [18] tackle flexible, on-demand flying mobile communications building upon 3D heterogeneous networks (HetNets) and focusing on beam control mechanisms, combining both mmWave and Wi-Fi access technologies. The concept of Wireless Environment-as-a-Service is introduced by the authors in [19]; flexible 3D networks are targeted via the utilisation of flexible RIS devices, organized in a network of space-time reconfigurable mirrors, orchestrated together by advanced algorithms running on ad-hoc controllers to dynamically change the propagation settings of the installed RISs, based on real-time/predicted network dynamics.

A wireless mesh backhauling solution using RISs is proposed by the authors in [20]. The introduced flexibility offers several desired features that can be exploited to overcome some of the backhauling challenges, particularly the severe attenuation at high frequencies. Due to the high temporal and spatial dynamics of the wireless traffic, Pirmagomedov et al. [21] propose making use of UE-based mmWave-based mesh interworking in the place of moving cells for increasing the flexibility in collaborative sharing, compute offloading, etc. Li et al. [22] introduce a novel 3D cellular model consisting of aerial base stations and aerial UEs, by integrating the coordinated multi-point (CoMP) transmission technique with the theory of stochastic geometry.

From a higher layer perspective, Bojovic et al. [23] propose to increase 5G/6G Core flexibility by customizing and optimizing network slices and introducing a higher level of programmability through dynamic queue management. The proposed works builds upon the SDN and NFV technologies which increase network programmability and

introduce the Network-as-a-Service (NaaS) concept. Ericson et al. [24] propose an evolved network architecture, which relies on cloudification, where shared generic hardware replaces dedicated hardware to improve flexibility and reduce total cost of ownership, jointly with cloud-optimized network architecture, and more flexible deployments comprising macro base stations, mesh networks, satellites, private networks, as well as connectivity using sub-THz frequencies. Dedicat 6G EU project [25], which encompasses part of the present work, targets dynamic resourcing and with dynamic coverage extension as part of a flexible 3D network being of the core objectives.

As it becomes apparent, there has already been a considerable number of efforts -both from the standardization as well as the literature perspectives- towards increasing the network flexibility for ubiquitous coverage and seamless service provisioning. Nevertheless, so far, the solutions, which are presented attempt to optimize specific aspects of the 3D continuum and omit to draw the overall picture of the required steps that will lead to the envisioned, disruptive paradigm. In the following section, an overview of the key requirements towards the envisioned 3D connectivity continuum is elaborated, along with a discussion on the most critical technical enablers, which are envisioned.

III. KEY CHALLENGES

A network of networks is defined as a network capable of flexibly integrating and managing diverse sub-networks and systems, heterogeneous communication technologies and connectivity resources and infrastructure, computing resources -including (far) edge ones-, as well as management and orchestration frameworks -under a coordinated, seamless coordination- over the whole 3D continuum. Thus, one of the most challenging aspects that the envisioned paradigm needs to address is the unification of those diverse network in a seamless manner, to ultimately operate as one RAN. Communication protocols will need to be redesigned as well; for example, the unification of NTN will inevitably have a considerable impact on the 6G Layer 3 and Layer 4 protocol design.

One of the most critical aspects concerns the seamless management and orchestration of ultra-challenging 6G services, efficiently exploiting a pool of 3D network connectivity and computing resources. The envisioned 3D network will comprise on the one hand a number of well-established (static) RAN deployments (5G and beyond NR infrastructure, coexisting with legacy solutions such as 4G RAN), but -most importantly- on the other hand, it will need to seamlessly integrate (and release) in a seamless manner dynamic or moving deployments, often with stochastic behavior; those deployments will be enabled by NTNs, airborne, maritime, underwater or even underground network elements. The latter makes the need for exposing, discovering, and managing those resources in swift manner. Additionally, it requires unified, software-defined control approaches to coordinate different tech-specific controllers (e.g., RIC for the RAN, SDN controller for terrestrial backhaul segments) and NTN platforms.

The integration of diverse topologies and -potentially 3rd party- network infrastructure in such a timely and seamless manner also calls for utmost reliability, trust, availability,

and resilience. Decentralized topologies, such as non-hierarchical structures such as mesh topologies, will require efficient ways for the network to rapidly verify the trustworthiness, reliability, and availability of the different resources. Also, the openness of the architecture that is envisioned will inevitably increase the attach surface of the end-to-end system. As a result, means for efficiently and “objectively” measuring and verifying the above indicators is critical.

IV. KEY TECHNICAL ENABLERS

Towards addressing the above challenges, a set of novel network capabilities must be introduced. As presented in Section II, standardization efforts, along with the research community have already paved the way for the evolution of novel features that will enable flexible networks to flourish. Below, the most critical technologies and potential solutions that will enable this transition are discussed.

A. Dissagregated, software-based NTN towards NTN Infrastructure-as-a-Service (NTN-IaaS)

The goal of rapid and autonomous service creation, deployment, activation, and management, resulting from new and ever-changing user and application requirements is still elusive. Research activity in this area has focused on the synergy of several concepts: programmable infrastructure, virtualization, open interfaces, and platforms, increasing degrees of intelligence inside the network, as well as flexible physical layer enablers.

Infrastructure programmability has been proposed as a solution for the fast, flexible, and dynamic deployment of new services. Programmable infrastructures allow the functionality of some of their elements to be programmed dynamically; this refers to executable code that is injected into an appropriate element to create the new functionality at run time. The basic idea is to enable 3rd parties (end users, operators, and service providers) to inject application-specific services (in the form of code) into the infrastructure, as a promising way of realizing application-specific service logic or performing dynamic service provision on demand. Viable programming architectures for programmable infrastructure must be carefully engineered to achieve suitable trade-offs between flexibility, performance, security, and manageability.

The answer lies in the promising potential that emerges with the advent of programmable infrastructure in the following aspects: rapid deployment of new services, customization of existing service features, scalability and cost reduction in the network and service management, information infrastructure and service integration, diversification of services and business opportunities.

Fig. 1 NTN Infrastructure-as-a-Service concept for flexible 3D networks

Unified software-defined control approaches to coordinate different tech-specific resource controllers (e.g., RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC) for the RAN, SDN Controller for terrestrial backhaul segments, NTN platform-specific controllers, etc.) must be (re-)designed, exposing programmable APIs (e.g., resource management, monitoring and control APIs) to guarantee seamless network segments’ integration in terms of network slices provisioning and re-configuration, ultimately enabling the NTN Infrastructure-as-a-Service (NTN IaaS) paradigm (Fig. 1).

B. Nomadic IAB-enabled nodes with virtualized RAN and functional split capabilities

Multi-hop wireless connectivity, along with potentially multiple connectivity options per node is considered a necessity when targeting to increase the network coverage as well as capacity in a flexible manner. The above leverages on existing networking technologies like device-to-device (D2D) and mesh topologies. Mesh topologies, seamlessly integrated by the overall network have the potential to radically improve performance indicators; especially, when leveraging MEC resources for e.g., offloading challenging computational tasks. An initial concept is illustrated in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2 D2D and mesh networking concepts for flexible networks

As also thoroughly presented in Section II, recognizing the importance of facilitating such deployments, 3GPP has already standardized the IAB solution over the 5G NR. Following the same rationale (as well as 3GPP terminology on IAB nodes/donors), the concept is extended towards NTN, nomadic IAB-enabled nodes (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Enhanced NTN-IAB functionality with a) different NTN-IAB node configurations, b) different CU-DU split options

Besides the IAB capability, the virtualized RAN enables different functional splits: The NTN-IAB donors, which refer to the network entities that have fiber or wired backhaul to the 5G Core of the network and the NTN-IAB nodes, which refer to the network elements/nodes that offer relaying capabilities and use one or more wireless backhaul links towards NTN-IAB donors, or other NTN-IAB nodes. The specific architecture has been designed to have minimal

impact on the 5GC/6GC (and its related signaling overhead), as well as low processing and design complexity at an IAB-node. Each NTN-IAB node hosts a DU, while it may also contain a UE part called mobile termination (NTN-MT). It is responsible for the lower layers of the radio interface to UEs or downstream MTs (of other IAB-nodes). The NTN-IAB donor hosts a distributed unit (DU) and the centralized unit (CU) that handles the control and upper layers of the radio interfaces. The NTN-IAB-donor-CU is responsible for the route management and the IAB network topology definition. The NTN-IAB-donor-CU may also offer distributed radio resource management capabilities for the specific network segment.

C. Management and orchestration of nomadic, D2D and mesh network deployments

In order to seamlessly and flexibly integrate heterogeneous, decentralized topologies, potentially comprising also 3rd party network infrastructure, and towards (NTN) IaaS, the envisioned network of networks must ensure that certain resources are considered trusted and reliable. Certain interfaces need to be defined to control and interact with the far-edge devices for resource exposure, synchronization, reachability verification, etc. At the same time, integration with the network and service management and orchestration framework is required; this will require proper abstraction of the D2D-mesh network topologies to the orchestration layer, discoverability, trust verification, as well as nodes' status monitoring (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 Node discovery, management, and orchestration in nomadic, D2D, and mesh network deployments

Furthermore, 3D MEC compute resource availability offered from mesh (N)TN topologies will offer great gains towards performance amelioration in numerous cases, where data needs to be processed and/or control decisions need to be taken rapidly in areas, where centralized resources (e.g., terrestrial cloud center) are remote, scarce or often non-existent.

On top of the above, highly intelligent algorithms are required for node/edge resources selection, access/backhaul traffic steering/switching/splitting, latency minimization, computation offloading, etc. This leads to the next critical enabler of the envisioned system, i.e., the native network intelligence.

D. Native, decentralized network intelligence

To improve network functionalities and deliver extreme flexibility and performance in terms of traditional Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), such as data rate, latency and reliability, AI/ML is considered as a *no alternative* enabler. 3GPP's NWDAF and Management Data Analytics Function (MDAF) [26][27] are considered the first steps

towards this direction -since Rel.16- enabling Network Functions (NFs) to access the MNO-driven analytics for different purposes, including intelligent slice selection and control. In more recent 3GPP working items [28], the aspects to be considered in relation to the potential extension of the current NWDAF functionalities towards distributed operations are described, such as whether NWDAF functional split is required, as well as which NWDAF functionality can be separated or placed in a different NF/NF Service.

The main challenge of is to design the (N)TN AI functions as inherent components of the system, rather than external services, and take those AI operations into consideration in all control plane- and data plane-related function design. Additionally, the resource scarcity that may characterize remote, underserved areas, poses challenging limitations in relation to the AI capabilities and the compute-connect-energy consumption tradeoffs that may result. In this sense, an (N)TN edge computing entity – such as the compute resources of a flying drone – may serve as a critical enabler, which however must be orchestrated carefully and considering a plethora of resource-related parameters in the end-to-end resource allocation and orchestration processes.

To this end, a novel federated AI architecture is required, that will enable decentralized AI functions to operate and coordinate with each other, spanning the whole connectivity-compute continuum of the 3D network. The enabling architecture must introduce optimal ways to share trained data models between multiple NWDAF/MDAF instances, specify the interactions that require standardized interfaces with the distributed NWDAF/MDAF architecture, as well identify the optimal network locations/entities, which can host distributed NWDAF/MDAF instances, along with the implications in relation to data privacy, signaling overhead minimization, as well as resource allocation decision-making conflict mitigation and coordination.

E. Physical layer advancements

Besides the architectural and management aspects, flexibility will largely rely on the advancement of a number of critical physical layer-related solutions as well. Intelligent reflecting/reconfigurable surfaces (IRSs), cell-free massive MIMO (CF-mMIMO) and (sub-)THz communications are some key enablers, which introduce disruptive potential and gains but at the same time exhibit a number of critical challenges [29]. For example, dynamic reflection response of the IRS is particularly important and will need both low-power semi-conductor elements, as well as ultra-low latency AI for sensing and configuring the IRS elements accordingly. CF-mMIMO is a very promising solution for overcoming the boundary effects of cellular networks; particularly for flexible networks, comprising also nomadic networks with stochastic behavior, network planning becomes ultra-challenging. Key challenges related to this enabler relates to novel user-centric approaches for transforming the CF paradigm to a scalable solution, in which based on each device's/user's context, only a sub-set of access points (APs) -as well as MECs- serve the users. Advanced AI techniques (e.g., Deep Reinforcement Learning solutions are very promising towards such directions). Scalable power control is also critical since it

controls the near-far effects and the inter-user interference for optimizing different KPIs.

Regarding higher frequency bands, 6G systems will rely on mmWave (30 to 300 GHz), THz technologies (300GHz to 3 THz), as well as Free space optics (FSO) for delivering data rates exceeding 10 Gbps. Novel transceiver designs will be required combining also compact physical sizes and power efficiency, while hybrid beamforming will be a critical enabler to implement large number of antenna elements along with high efficiency amplifiers. Last but not least, signal processing in massively populated or decentralized (cell-free) networks will need to cope with numerous novel challenges, such as training overhead reduction in pilot-based estimation or adaptive filtering in beamforming for high-dimensional 6G scenarios.

V. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Entering the initial, design phase of the 6G era, principles such as ultra-high flexibility, programmability, openness, and controllability are considered indispensable for the design of the future network. This article has identified some of the most critical research challenges towards realizing the envisioned 3D, flexible network of networks, along with some key technical enablers and research directions that will lead to their realization.

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